

A Case for a European Lunar Exploration Analysis Group. B. T. Greenhagen¹, ¹Lunar Exploration Analysis Group (leag.chair@gmail.com).

Introduction: Analysis Groups (AGs) are critical community organizations that facilitate and mediate the relationship between stakeholders (e.g., NASA's Planetary Science Division) and their communities of subject matter experts (e.g., the lunar exploration community in government, industry, non-profit research centers, and academia). The recent 'reimagining' of NASA PSD's relationship with their AGs, including the Lunar Exploration Analysis Group (LEAG), has eliminated a dedicated line of financial support and encouraged the AGs to exist and act independently [1]. As the AGs evolve to the new environment, there are opportunities to evaluate opportunities for further engagement and activities. Here, I will describe the historical value of AGs, including LEAG, and make a case for the creation of a European Lunar Analysis Group (E-LEAG) bespoke to European community and stakeholders.

Analysis Groups: In May 2025, the chairs of NASA's planetary AGs jointly issued a statement that described general and historical benefits of AGs, titled 'The Keys of AGness' [2]. This document lays out the case for AGs along four key areas:

1. AGs serve as community voices, provide interdisciplinary forums, identify needs, and form consensus opinions.
2. AGs are custodians of their communities, build networks, share knowledge, and help develop the next generation.
3. AGs are a necessary repository of resources and institutional memory, which guide interdisciplinary prioritization through activities such as Decadal Surveys.
4. AGs are a respected conduit for two-way communication with NASA to broaden and amplify important information exchange.

The Keys of AGness outlines important contributions from each AG in the preceding decade. Related to LEAG, the document details the following:

- 11 NASA-directed Specific Action Teams and Reports (2014 – 2025)
- 1 LEAG-directed Specific Action Team and Report (2022)
- Lunar Science Goals Activity (in review)
- The United States Lunar Exploration Roadmap (2016)
- NASA-requested response to lunar coordinate system (2023)

In total, the Keys of AGness makes a compelling case for the value of AGs. This model has demonstrated as highly successful. And the model should be transferable to other space agencies.

LEAG: LEAG is currently implementing plans to maintain its high-quality work in the new environment. These activities include revising our char-

ter, launching a new website, establishing a new email list, identifying options for future meetings, and evaluating opportunities for expanded scope.

International coordination is an obvious area to investigate. And the new autonomy of LEAG allows for more direct organizational partnerships than the previous framework. At the same time, the resources that LEAG is developing (website, email list) could potentially be used to help rapidly establish partners.

E-LEAG: The formation of a European-centric LEAG is appropriate given the high value that ESA and member space agencies have on lunar exploration. Important functions of E-LEAG could include:

- Be a critical focusing mechanism that enables the European community to speak with a singular voice.
- Support the essential pipeline of expertise that is vital to identifying and nurturing the best talent to achieve ESA's lunar exploration and science goals.
- Address lunar exploration concerns from a distinctly European-centric posture that uniquely aligns with ESA's organization and goals.

These are the same functions that LEAG has historically performed and seeks to maintain in the USA; therefore, E-LEAG could be stood up with wide range of support levels (or no support) from ESA or member space agencies.

Collaboration: While LEAG and an E-LEAG would naturally prioritize the needs of our stakeholder communities, there would be ample opportunity for collaboration.

1. To ensure coordination, LEAG and E-LEAG could each host a representative of the partner group on their executive committees.
2. On topics of mutual interest, memberships of analysis activities (e.g., specific action teams, white papers, etc.) could include representation of both groups.
3. Sharing of resources related to websites, mailing lists, and community development.
4. Co-sponsorship of annual meetings.

Working together, LEAG and E-LEAG could provide valuable community analysis vital to international exploration of the Moon, in ways that are distinct from other agency-aligned organizations.

References:

- [1] <https://science.nasa.gov/planetary-science/resources/psd-director-letter-to-the-community/>
- [2] https://www.lpi.usra.edu/analysis/Keys_of_A_Gness_Final_Document.pdf